

DIGITISING AND TRANSFORMING THE EUROPEAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

01 Are you a manager for a construction site?

02 Do you already use sensor devices to collect data for your site but miss the integration within a decision-making platform?

03 Are you interested in implementing sensor-based monitoring?

YES ?

Then our ASHVIN project proposes you an opportunity to create a digital twin of your construction site

FREE OF CHARGE

- Ignite a monitoring plan
- Support sensor installation on site
- Provide a digital twin platform (beta version) for project monitoring

FOR MORE INFORMATION

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